

PINK TAX AND FEMININE BRANDING: AWARENESS, MOTIVATIONS, AND PERCEPTION OF FILIPINA YOUTH CONSUMERS IN CAUAYAN CITY, ISABELA²

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the level of awareness, motivating factors, and overall perception of Filipina youth regarding the pink tax, a pricing phenomenon wherein products marketed to women, often using the color pink, were more expensive than comparable men's products. Despite the prevalence of pink marketing strategies, the pink tax remained underexplored in the Philippines. The study aimed to understand the extent of awareness, driving factors, and overall perception of Filipina youth on the pink tax, as well as the correlations among awareness, driving factors, and perception of pink products affected by pink tax, caused by pink marketing strategies. A quantitative-descriptive research design was employed, with a correlational research design used to identify relationships among variables, such as respondents' awareness of pink tax, motivating factors influencing their purchase of pink products, and their overall perception. The study concluded that Filipina youth consumers were aware of feminine branding and pink marketing strategies, as well as the pink tax applied to products intended for women. Awareness primarily came from their use of social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. The study revealed a significant positive correlation between awareness of feminine branding, pink products, and pink tax, along with driving factors influencing respondents' purchase decisions and their overall perception of pink tax. It also found that awareness of feminine branding and pink tax influenced respondents' perspectives on whether pink tax had positive or negative effects. Those perceiving pink tax positively believed pink products were higher quality, while those perceiving it negatively found it unfair, insulting, and discriminatory. The study recommended that the government, particularly the legislative body, study the impact of pink tax on consumers and utilize this research to develop relevant legislation addressing the pink tax phenomenon.

Keywords: *feminine branding, pink tax, pink products, pink marketing strategy, Filipina youth consumers*

INTRODUCTION

Women have shaped communities and civilizations throughout history, impacting politics, economics, science, art, and culture. Traditionally, women were not given the chance to do certain things viewed as exclusively for men, such as the right to vote, the right to have an education, the right to work, or even the freedom to speak against injustices they may have experienced. But because of the changing times, women are now leading in different fields across the globe, such as in politics, business, sports, and many more that were dominated by men before (Pote, 2022). Although there have been changes in how women participate and are viewed in society, sexism still thrives in different aspects of human life. Traces of sexism still exist in today's society – these traces can be shown either through direct or indirect ways. One of these areas in which women were still oppressed can be seen through gender-based pricing (Abdou, 2019).

Price discrimination is the act where sellers sell the same kind of product to different buyers at varying prices depending on the kind of buyer. One of the types of price discrimination is known as "gender-based pricing" (Febriyanti & Yuwono, 2023). Gender-based pricing is a kind of discrimination in which some products are priced at higher costs depending on the client or customer's gender. In other words, this is the practice of charging different prices for goods or services based on the consumer's gender. Aside from being disadvantaged in the labor force, women are also disadvantaged as consumers – frequently paying substantially more than men for similar goods and services (Joint Economic Committee to the United States Congress, 2016).

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In the study by Abdou (2019), gender-based discrimination is so globally common that it has acquired its own term - "The Pink Tax". Pink tax refers to higher or more expensive prices of products targeted at women compared to products that are targeted at men (Moshary et al., 2023). These distinctions are merely made because of small details, like the color "pink," included in the product which denotes that women are the target market for these goods (Abdou, 2019). Historically, the Pink Tax derives its name from the historical prevalence of pink-colored things promoted to women. This has resulted in individuals being led to believe that a product marketed to women needs to have more intricate aesthetics to be profitable (Habbal, 2020).

Moreover, the products affected by the pink tax are generally known as pink products and are marketed by different companies through different strategies mainly known as "pink marketing". Pink marketing is a strategy to collect marketing information based on women's viewpoints and choices to tailor products to their wants and needs in the market for goods and services. All marketing initiatives addressing product, pricing, distribution, and customer promotion are represented in pink marketing (Zarei & Kharajo, 2022). For instance, a soap producer may provide two pricing points for essentially the same soap: a cheap blue bar and an expensive pink bar (Moshary et al., 2023). Furthermore, in the study of Ananya (2022), it was found that by fostering a variety of cultural expectations, popular media narratives significantly aid in the normalization of the pink tax. The paper delves into the relationship between gender norms and marketing tactics, concluding that women's economic, social, and political engagement have been impacted by the pink tax.

Due to the emergence and effect of the pink tax on the economic, social, and political engagements of women, some states or countries started the initiative to lobby bills into their legislative bodies concerning the pink tax. Particularly, the New York State Assembly and State Senate approved bill S2679 in 2019–2020, outlawing pricing based on gender. In 2022, California lawmakers passed AB 1287, a policy that is essentially the same. Intending to enact a comparable restriction across the state, Representative Jackie Speier has presented the Pink Tax Repeal Act in Congress four times since 2015. Regrettably, there is insufficient data on the pink tax to support legislative measures (Moshary et al., 2023).

In the Philippines, the topic of pink tax has not been sufficiently explored, with a notable lack of local articles or studies online. There has been no thorough examination or in-depth analysis of the subject (Chua et al., 2022). This study aims to address this gap by contributing to local research on the pink tax. It seeks to determine the level of awareness, driving factors, and overall perception of Filipina youth regarding pink tax, as well as the correlation among these aspects and their impact on pink products influenced by pink marketing strategies. Specifically, this research will explore the level of awareness of Filipina youth consumers in Cauayan City, Isabela, on the pink tax imposed by pink marketing strategies, identify the driving factors or motivations behind their purchase of pink products, assess their overall perception of the pink tax, and examine any correlations among awareness, motivations, and perceptions related to the pink tax on pink products.

METHODS

The researchers employed descriptive quantitative research to identify the extent of awareness among the respondents regarding pink tax, driving factors, and overall perception. Additionally, they utilized a correlational research design to explore relationships among variables such as awareness of pink tax, driving factors, and overall perception.

Respondents were selected using purposive and convenience sampling methods. Based on the Philippine Statistics Authority's (PSA) population census report as of 2020, Cauayan City has a population of 143,403. The sample size was determined by multiplying the total population by 20% to represent youth aged 15-30, divided by 2 for female youth, with a 7% margin of error and 95% confidence level, resulting in a minimum sample size of 194. The study was conducted in Cauayan City, Isabela, Region II, limiting participants to 194 female youth consumers aged 15 to 30, in accordance with Section II of Republic Act 8044, the Youth in Nation-Building Act, who have resided in Cauayan City for at least one year.

Researchers used an online survey questionnaire via Google Forms and printed versions, incorporating both close-ended and open-ended response options to gauge event frequency and percentage. A 5-point Likert scale was primarily used for responses, adapted from existing studies on pink tax and tailored to the study's research questions. Data collected were anonymized, with only email addresses required for online survey validation.

Statistical analyses included percentage, frequency count, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson's R. Percentage data were employed to assess awareness levels of respondents on feminine branding, pink products, and pink tax. Mean and standard deviation were used to determine sources of information/knowledge on feminine

branding, pink products, pink tax, driving factors, and perception. Pearson's *r* was employed to explore correlations among these variables.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Awareness of Respondents on Feminine Branding

Table 1 shows respondents awareness level regarding companies that use marketing strategies targeted at women or "feminine branding." The majority (53.1%) of the respondents are aware of feminine branding, while only 5.2% are unaware of it. Moreover, 32% of the respondents are slightly mindful of feminine branding, and 9.8% of the respondents are very aware of it.

Table 1. Awareness of Respondents on Feminine Branding.

Awareness on Feminine Branding	Participants	Percentage
Unaware	10	5.2%
Slightly Aware	62	32.0%
Aware	103	53.1%
Very Aware	19	9.8%

Note. The total in might not be equal to 100% due to rounding errors.

The findings indicate that half of the respondents were aware of the feminine branding and most of them were aware of feminine branding. This shows that respondents have reasonable amount of awareness of feminine branding as they are aware and only a few of them were very aware, slightly aware, and unaware. This manifests that respondents do not have an in-depth or high degree level of awareness on feminine branding. In addition, this indicates that feminine branding is a well- recognized concept among the majority. However, there is still a small but notable portion of the population that lacks awareness, suggesting opportunities for targeted educational and marketing efforts to enhance understanding and engagement across all awareness levels.

Sources of Respondents' Information on Feminine Branding

Table 2 shows that respondents often encounter feminine branding on social media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube), with a mean of 4.11. The lowest source of respondents' information or knowledge was books/articles/journals/magazines.

Table 2. Sources of Respondents' Information on Feminine Branding.

Sources of Information on Feminine Branding	Mean	SD	QD
a. In Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Youtube)	4.11	1.149	Often
b. In school/university/work	3.35	1.249	Sometimes
c. In books/article/journal/magazine	3.16	1.181	Sometimes
d. Through a friend/acquaintance	3.4	1.247	Sometimes

Results show that feminine branding is often seen by respondents on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Youtube. The awareness of respondents regarding feminine branding may be linked to their use of social media platforms as majority of them encounter said feminine branding through the above-mentioned social media platforms. This underscores the crucial role of social media as a contributor on women's awareness of feminine branding as companies use social media in marketing their products. However, this also shows that since the lowest source of respondents' information or knowledge was in

books/article/journal/magazine. This indicates either respondents do not usually spend their time reading books/articles/journal/magazines or feminine branding is not seen or talked about in said reading materials.

Over the past years, there has been a significant increase in the use of social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp. (Chen & Qasim, 2021) As social media has brought a new way of communication and collaboration where interpersonal and intrapersonal communication can be fostered (Kutu et al., 2022), marketing companies use social media to increase their brand awareness. Most firms employ Internet marketing techniques to increase customer brand awareness, including controlling user-generated content, advertising on social media platforms, and blogger endorsements. (Wang & Kim, 2017)

Moreover, according to Johnson's (2015) study, social media is one of the most essential components of women's promotional mix on the internet, where most women spend their time—nearly 89% of women have profiles on social networks. In the study of Massoudi et al. (2020), marketers consider the purchasing decisions made by female consumers because women are influential and involved in decision-making regarding the goods and services of others, including friends, family, co-workers, and the people around them.

Awareness of Respondents on Pink Products

Table 3 shows that the majority of respondents (52.6%) are aware that certain products are marketed to women through their slim packaging and use feminine colors such as pink and violet, or, to simplify, the "pink products". On the other hand, only 3.1% of the total respondents need to be made aware of the pink products.

Table 3. Awareness of Respondents on Pink Products.

Awareness on Pink Products	Participants	Percentage
Unaware	6	3.1%
Slightly Aware	57	29.4%
Aware	102	52.6%
Very Aware	29	14.9%

The findings show that half of the respondents were aware that certain products are marketed to women through its slim packaging and by using feminine colors such as pink and violet or to simplify what researchers about the pink tax call the "pink products". This shows that respondents have reasonable amount of awareness of pink products as they are aware and only a few of them were very aware, slightly aware, and unaware. Their awareness comes from their use of different social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and Youtube. This manifests that respondents do not have an in-depth or high degree level of awareness on pink products. In addition, this indicates that pink products are a well-recognized concept among the majority. However, there is still a small but notable portion of the population that lacks awareness, suggesting opportunities for targeted educational and marketing efforts to enhance understanding and engagement on pink products across all awareness levels.

Kardetoff's (2022) study of gender-based products in the Swedish market, focusing on 12 hygiene products, revealed that women usually buy products similar to men, with the only differences being the color and the packaging. They are aware that products with pink color and slim packaging are products for women. Thus, they buy pink products because they are aware that these products are tailored exactly to their needs.

Pink Products Encountered by Respondents

Table 4 shows the following categories of pink products respondents encountered in the past six (6) months. Respondents often encounter pink products that are more expensive for women than men: skin care products, hair care products, cosmetics, clothing, shoes/slippers, medicine/vitamins, and bags. Furthermore, respondents sometimes encounter the following pink products: school or office supplies and children's toys.

Products such as skin care products, hair care products, cosmetics, clothing, shoes/slippers, medicine/vitamins, and bags are usually seen as pink products. This is because these products were often marketed toward women. These products were tailored to their needs such as using slim and not bulky packaging with light colors or the color pink to make it attractive to women or advertising it to women making it appear that these products were made for them only. Moreover, products such as school or office supplies and children's toys

are only sometimes seen or encountered pink products as these products may be used by different genders regardless if they are in color pink or slim.

Table 4. Pink Products Encountered by Respondents

Kinds of Pink Products	Mean	SD	QD
a. Skincare	4.07	1.222	Often
b. Hair care	4.1	1.031	Often
c. Cosmetics	4.02	1.209	Often
d. Clothing	4.15	0.996	Often
e. School or office supplies	3.47	1.157	Sometimes
f. Children's toys	3.11	1.232	Sometimes
g. Shoes/slippers	3.86	1.11	Often
h. Medicine/Vitamins	3.64	1.239	Often
i. Bags	3.92	1.16	Often

The study by Bessendorf (2015) showed the first-ever investigation into New York's gender pricing of goods city spanning several industries conducted by the New York City Department of Consumer Affairs (DCA). Said study measured the price variations that male and female consumers encounter while purchasing similar goods. For adult clothing, women's apparel costs approximately 8% more than men's on average. A single typical item cost \$307.38 for women and \$285.85 for men overall, a \$21.53 disparity. The most considerable average price disparity was found in shirts, where women had to pay about 15% more for each shirt, or an average of \$3.72 more. Dress shirts trailed closely after, with an average price difference of \$6.65 per shirt, while for women, they cost roughly 13 percent more. For personal care products, women pay 13% more on average than men do for personal care items. The hair care category showed the most significant average price disparity, with women paying almost 48% more for items (an average of \$2.71 more per set of shampoo and conditioner). The study then concluded that a female customer experiences markups to varying degrees throughout her career. Products for infants and kids had the lowest price differences, adult personal care items the highest, and adult apparel and senior products in the center, with nearly equal price differences by percentage. This is noteworthy, considering that a consumer's "adult" stage of life lasts longer than any other stage of the lifecycle. Furthermore, compared to all other consumer goods categories in this study, adults use personal care products more frequently. Given that the average cost of personal care items is 13 percent more for women than for males, these differences would have a substantially more significant financial impact over a female consumer's lifetime.

The above-cited study supports the findings in Table 7, which show that products such as skin care products, hair care products, cosmetics, clothing, shoes/slippers, medicine/vitamins, and bags were considered pink products or products targeted to women that are more expensive compared to products targeted to men.

Awareness of Respondents on Pink Tax

Table 5 shows that the majority of respondents (47.4%) are aware that certain companies increase the price of products that have the same quality that is targeted to women compared to men or, in general, the "pink tax." 14.4% of the respondents are unaware, 31.4% of them are slightly aware, and the remaining 6.7% are very unaware of the pink tax.

Table 5. Awareness of Respondents on Pink Tax.

Awareness on Pink Tax	Participants	Percentage
Unaware	28	14.4%
Slightly Aware	61	31.4%
Aware	92	47.4%
Very Aware	13	6.7%

The results show that almost half of the respondents were aware that certain companies increase the price of products which have the same quality that are targeted to women compared to men or in general, the “pink tax”. This shows that respondents have reasonable amount of awareness of pink tax as they are aware and only a few of them were very aware, slightly aware, and unaware. This manifests that respondents do not have an in-depth or high degree level of awareness on pink tax. In addition, this indicates that the pink tax is a well-recognized concept among the majority. However, there is still a small but notable portion of the population that lacks awareness on this matter, suggesting opportunities for targeted educational and marketing efforts to enhance understanding and engagement across all awareness levels.

In Sanadhya's study (2022), university students identified gender-based price discrimination, especially on products such as clothing and services such as haircuts. The study also concluded that as women advanced in age, they could grasp the concept of the pink tax, although it appears that they had never heard of or knew of the existence of the pink tax.

Sources of Respondents' Information on Pink Tax

Table 6 indicates that respondents often encounter the pink tax on social media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, YouTube), with a mean of 3.56. The lowest source of respondents' information or knowledge was in books/articles/journals/magazines, with a mean of 2.86.

Table 6. Sources of Respondents' Information on Pink Tax

Sources of Information on Feminine Branding	Mean	SD	QD
a. In Social Media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, Youtube)	3.56	1.307	Often
b. In school/university/work	2.96	1.186	Sometimes
c. In books/article/journal/magazine	2.86	1.221	Sometimes
d. Through a friend/acquaintance	2.98	1.221	Sometimes

The awareness of respondents regarding the pink tax may be linked to their use of social media platforms as the majority of them encounter said pink tax through the above- mentioned social media platforms. Social media platforms as the top source of respondents' awareness of the pink tax also shows their usage or time spend on these platforms. This underscores the crucial role of social media as a contributor on women's awareness of the pink tax as companies use social media in marketing their products. However, this also shows that since the lowest source of respondents' information or knowledge on the pink tax was in books/article/journal/magazine. This indicates either respondents do not usually spend their time reading books/articles/journal/magazines or feminine branding is not seen or talked about in said reading materials.

In the same study by Johnson (2015) cited above, social media is one of the most important components of women's promotional mix on the internet, where the majority of women spend their time—nearly 89% of women have profiles on social networks. Chua et al. (2022) study supports this, stating that Filipina youth knew the concept of the pink tax from social media, schools, their peers, and the different literature they read.

The above-mentioned studies support the data in Table 9 that the pink tax is often encountered or heard on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Instagram, and YouTube. Women's reported increase in

social media use may be one reason why social media platforms are the source where they often encounter the pink tax.

Driving Factors of Respondents in Buying Pink Products

Table 7 shows the driving factors of respondents in buying pink products. The number one factor which drives respondents in buying pink products is because the color pink is attractive.

Table 7. Driving Factors of Respondents in Buying Pink Products

Driving Factors	Mean	SD	QD
1. I buy pink products because the color "pink" is attractive.	3.77	0.955	Often
2. I buy pink products because I feel that this is associated with my femininity.	3.68	0.889	Often
3. I buy pink products because they are intended for me as a woman.	3.63	1.036	Often
4. I buy pink products because I am already used to buying pink products.	3.54	0.987	Often
5. I do not buy pink products because I am aware that it is only a marketing strategy by companies.	2.93	0.998	Sometimes
6. I do not buy pink products because they are more expensive than normal products.	2.93	0.955	Sometimes
7. I do not buy pink products because the color of the products or their packaging does not matter to me.	3.17	1.042	Sometimes

The attractiveness of the color pink is supported by the study of Kodžoman et al., (2021) stating that pink was the most preferred color of their respondents in the age range of 25 to 34 years old. On the other hand, results also show that the most minor factors driving respondents to buy pink products are awareness that it is only a marketing strategy by companies and that pink products are more expensive than standard products. These results are supported by the study of Chua et al. (2022), which shows that women who were aware of the marketing strategy of companies targeting them are not willing to buy pink products anymore. Furthermore, the study of Chua et al. (2022) revealed that women do not purchase pink products such as pink-colored razors because they have the same quality as regular razors but are more expensive.

The results show that the highest driving factor motivating respondents to buy pink products is that pink is attractive to women. This driving factor often affects women's purchasing behavior of pink products, as pink is deeply rooted in the notion that pink is for girls and blue is for boys. This is also connected to their womanhood, reflecting their femininity. This underscores that companies target women through their femininity and that women are attracted when these factors are satisfied. On the other hand, when women are aware of the pink marketing strategy or the feminine branding, this awareness affects their driving factors in buying pink products.

Respondents' Perception of Pink Tax

Majority (65) of the respondents view the pink tax neutrally, meaning they see it as neither positive nor negative. Respondent 27 stated that she does not really look at prices because she buys products depending on her needs.

Secondly, 60 respondents view the pink tax negatively, while 25 respondents perceive the pink tax very negatively. Respondent 130 supported this perception, stating: "I strongly disagree because it is unfair for some women like me." The same sentiment was expressed by Respondent 131, who finds the pink tax massively wrong because companies are taking advantage of women who show femininity by choosing colors that correspond to it.

Moreover, Respondent 165 finds the pink tax discriminatory and alienating. As Respondent 172 also views the pink tax negatively, she stated: "It is entirely an insult for women to be offered products or services that are more expensive than men just because of this pink branding. In light of gender equality, women should have products or services at affordable prices on par with men."

On the other hand, 23 respondents view the pink tax positively, and 21 respondents perceive the pink tax very positively. Respondent 114 views the pink tax positively, explaining that some feminine products are more expensive than men's because they have more added ingredients compared to men's products.

Correlation Among Awareness, Driving Factors, and Perception

A Pearson r correlation coefficient analysis was conducted to explore relationships between awareness of feminine branding, awareness of pink products, and awareness of pink tax among respondents. Results indicated significant positive correlations between awareness of feminine branding and awareness of pink products ($r=0.374$, $p<0.001$), awareness of feminine branding and awareness of pink tax ($r=0.475$, $p<0.001$), and awareness of pink products and awareness of pink tax ($r=0.348$, $p<0.001$). This suggests that higher awareness of feminine branding correlates with greater awareness of pink products and pink tax among respondents.

Awareness of feminine branding, pink products, and pink tax influences purchasing decisions, particularly among women who perceive these products as tailored to their femininity. Marketing strategies utilizing feminine branding, such as the color pink, can enhance brand recognition and consumer identification. These strategies appeal to emotional connections and social influences, shaping perceptions and driving factors influencing purchasing behavior (Vacas de Carvalho et al., 2020; Chua et al., 2022; Ridgway & Myers, 2014; Li et al., 2015; Alubaidi, 2016).

Table 8. Correlation Matrix of awareness, driving factors, and perception

		Feminine Branding	Pink Products	Pink Tax	Driving Factors	Overall Perception
Feminine Branding	Pearson's r	—				
	p-value	—				
Pink Products	Pearson's r	0.374	—			
	p-value	<.001	—			
Pink Tax	Pearson's r	0.475	0.348	—		
	p-value	<.001	<.001	—		
Driving Factors	Pearson's r	0.145	0.305	0.36	—	
	p-value	0.043	<.001	<.001	—	
Overall Perception	Pearson's r	0.171	0.15	0.306	0.217	—
	p-value	0.017	0.037	<.001	0.002	—

Furthermore, there was a significant positive correlation between awareness of feminine branding, awareness of pink products, and awareness of pink tax, and the driving factors influencing respondents' decisions to purchase pink products ($r=0.145$, $p<0.043$; $r=0.304$, $p<0.001$; $r=0.360$, $p<0.001$). This indicates that heightened awareness of these elements increases the likelihood of purchasing decisions influenced by factors such as perceived quality and inclusivity (Chua et al., 2022).

Additionally, the study found significant positive correlations between awareness of feminine branding, awareness of pink products, awareness of pink tax, and respondents' perceptions of the pink tax ($r=0.171$, $p<0.017$; $r=0.150$, $p<0.037$; $r=0.306$, $p<0.001$). Consumers aware of feminine branding are more likely to recognize the pricing disparities between pink products marketed to women and similar products marketed to men, influencing their perceptions accordingly (Kumar & Prathyusha, 2023; Chua et al., 2022).

Moreover, there was a significant positive correlation between the driving factors influencing respondents' purchases of pink products and their perceptions of the pink tax ($r=0.217$, $p<0.002$). This suggests that stronger driving factors, such as emotional connections and perceived product quality, positively shape consumer perceptions of the pink tax (Chua et al., 2022).

CONCLUSION

Based on the results, the awareness of respondents on feminine branding affects their driving factors in buying pink products. More so, their awareness of the pink tax also affects their driving factors in purchasing pink products. Their awareness lead them to view that pink tax can either have good or bad effects for them. Those who view pink tax positively perceive that pink products are more expensive than men's products because they are of higher quality. On the other hand, respondents who view pink tax negatively perceive that this is unfair, insulting, and discriminatory. Their awareness of the feminine branding, pink, products, and the pink tax significantly correlate and affect their purchases and their perception of pink tax. Moreover, it revealed that respondents encounter the application of the pink marketing strategy or the feminine branding and the imposition of the pink tax on products such as skin care products, hair care products, cosmetics, clothing, shoes/slippers, medicine/vitamins, and bags.

Overall, the study provides input or a foundation of the succeeding researches on the emergence of pink tax on the Philippines. The data presented in this study may be an additional resource on pink tax in the local setting – the Philippines and in Cauayan City, Isabela, in particular. It may supplement the local literature and be added in the pool of information on feminine branding, pink products, and the pink tax as there is a clear deficiency in this area.

LIMITATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

This study has several limitations. Firstly, it focuses exclusively on women aged 15-30 residing in Cauayan City, Isabela. While the researchers selected 194 Filipina youth consumers, a larger sample size could have provided more comprehensive insights and broader perspectives. Generalizing the findings to a larger population of Filipina youth consumers may be constrained due to the small sample size. The researchers recommend conducting further research with a larger and more diverse population, including different genders and age groups.

Secondly, due to limited time and resources, this study only focused on Filipina youth consumers without considering their income, family background, and cultural influences. The researchers suggest further exploration of women's attitudes towards purchasing pink products, with an in-depth analysis of factors such as employment status, family background, and cultural context, which could influence their purchasing decisions. Additionally, cross-cultural studies could examine how cultural norms affect the effectiveness of feminine branding and consumer responses to the pink tax.

Lastly, the study did not investigate the long-term effects of the pink tax on consumer behavior and brand loyalty due to time constraints. Future research could explore these aspects to better understand the lasting impacts of the pink tax.

Despite these limitations, the study's findings are significant. Firstly, they reveal the level of awareness among Cauayaña youth consumers regarding feminine branding, pink products, and the pink tax. This awareness could serve as a basis for local government initiatives in Cauayan City to educate consumers about these phenomena. Secondly, the study highlights the perceptions and motivating factors influencing Cauayaña youth consumers' views on the pink tax. These insights can aid businesses and companies in developing targeted marketing strategies for women.

Lastly, the study identifies several avenues for future research, including cross-cultural investigations into the influence of cultural norms on feminine branding and consumer responses to the pink tax. It also suggests further exploration of the factors driving women to purchase pink products, considering their employment status, family background, and cultural influences. Continued research in these areas is essential to deepen understanding of the pink tax's effects and consumer behavior related to pink products.

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